

Perennial Plantings and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

Cover photo: Prairie strips, a possible implementation of Conservation Cover (327) and Contour Buffer Strips (332) discussed below, grow at the Iowa State University Armstrong Research Farm. Iowa State University, Extension and Outreach. https://www.extension.iastate.edu/news/files/eo-news/images/prairie_strips_at_the_isu_armstrong_research_farm.jpg.

About the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Purpose

The purpose of this technical guidance focusing on perennial planting practices is to provide an overview of their greenhouse gas (GHG) benefits. The NRCS conservation practice standards covered by this guidance include:

- Conservation Cover (327)
- Contour buffer strips (332)
- Field Border (386)
- Riparian Herbaceous Cover (390)
- Grassed Waterways (412)
- Wildlife Habitat Planting (420)
- Vegetative Barrier (601)
- Herbaceous Wind Barriers (603)

This guidance focuses on farm-scale effects rather than larger landscape to regional scales. As such, we do not focus on leakage issues (i.e., whether a shift to incorporate perennials at the farm-scale induces GHG emissions elsewhere), but rather emphasize the GHG and other environmental benefits that come with addressing on-farm resource concerns through perennial plantings (i.e., reducing nutrient run-off, taking non-productive land out of annual agriculture).

Background and Summary

There is strong scientific consensus that perennial plantings on agricultural lands can have substantial GHG benefits compared to cultivation of land for annual agriculture (Cates et al. 2016; Culman et al. 2010; Buma et al. 2024). Historically, the cultivation of land that was previously under perennial plantings (especially relevant to U.S. native prairie systems) has led to substantial declines in soil carbon stocks (DeLuca and Zabinski 2011). The transition from perennial to annual cropping systems results in a variety of changes, detailed below, that contribute to increased greenhouse emissions.

PRIMARY DRIVERS OF SOIL CARBON LOSS FROM CULTIVATION OF PERENNIAL SYSTEMS

Firstly, because of persistent plant cover and deeper rooting systems, perennial systems lead to increases in soil carbon through inputs of above-and below-ground carbon. Cultivation leads to substantial declines in soil carbon stocks due to reduced carbon inputs and microbial decomposition. When land under perennial plantings is converted to annual crops, soil carbon levels drop sharply due to reduced carbon inputs.

Secondly, the cultivation of perennial systems and the physical disturbance of tillage accelerates soil carbon decomposition by soil microbes. Tillage also disrupts soil structure, breaking apart protective soil aggregates which can lead to increased erosion, further depleting soil carbon pools. As soil structure breaks down, wind and water erosion due to bare soil surface can accelerate losses of soil and soil carbon from the system as well.

Finally, agricultural management practices necessary to maintain high levels of productivity in annual systems (e.g., fertilization and irrigation) also lead to increased emissions on land formerly under perennial cover.

RECOVERY OF SOIL CARBON FOLLOWING RESTORATION TO PERMANENT, PERENNIAL PLANT COVER

Perennial plants enhance soil carbon stocks due to several fundamental ecological mechanisms:

- **Continuous Plant Cover.** Perennial plants maintain continuous cover throughout the year, which reduces soil erosion and increases soil organic matter through sustained above- and below-ground litter and root inputs.
- **Deep Root Systems.** Perennial plants typically have deeper and more extensive root systems (i.e., root structure and length) compared to annual plants, building long-term root biomass stocks. These deep root systems contribute to carbon storage over a greater soil depth and enhance soil structure and microbial activity necessary for soil carbon stabilization.
- **Enhanced Soil Structure.** The root systems of perennial plants improve soil aggregation, which physically protects soil carbon from decomposition.

Figure 1. Perennial wheatgrass (left) versus annual (right), demonstrating increased root biomass stocks in the perennial system over the annual one. Photo credit: Crews and Rumsey 2017.

VARIATION OF MITIGATION OUTCOMES DUE TO INTERACTIONS WITH SOIL TYPE AND CLIMATE

The GHG impacts of changing land use and incorporating perennials can vary based on factors related to climate and parent material. Considering the variability introduced by these state factors is important to develop more tailored management practices aimed at reducing GHG impacts and enhancing soil carbon sequestration in different agroecosystems.

CLIMATE

Temperature and Precipitation. The climate of an area, especially its temperature and precipitation, plays a crucial role in the variation of soil carbon levels. Soil carbon content generally increases with higher precipitation and decreases with higher temperatures. This variation is mainly due to the effects of climate on primary productivity and decomposition rates.

Recovery Rates. The accrual of soil carbon in formerly cultivated lands that transition to perennial might be higher in areas with higher precipitation, due to increased net primary productivity (NPP) leading to higher C inputs into the soil.

PARENT MATERIAL

Soil texture and mineralogy. Parent material's physical properties, such as soil texture and mineralogy, can influence soil carbon accrual and stabilization. Soils with higher clay content may have higher capacity to stabilize and store soil carbon due to increased surface area and charged mineral surfaces (Cotrufo et al. 2013). The presence of clay and other minerals also promotes the formation of soil aggregates, which physically protect soil carbon from decomposition (McLauchlan 2006). Conversely, sandy soils are less capable of stabilizing soil carbon due to limited surface area, making them more susceptible to carbon losses through erosion and leaching. Thus, areas with different parent materials and soil compositions will exhibit varying capacities for soil carbon protection and accumulation post-agriculture.

General Effects of Perennial Plantings

Converting previously cultivated soils to perennial plantings is one of the most effective agricultural conservation strategies to build soil carbon and reduce emissions of nitrous oxide (N₂O), while also addressing other on-farm resource concerns. Current scientific consensus at the global scale estimates average soil carbon storage rates of 0.33 – 1.01 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Crews and Rumsey 2017), with the U.S. and Canada falling on the lower end of that range (McLauchlan 2006). Assessed in percentage change, a recent global meta-analysis estimated soil carbon increases of 10-37% when converting cultivated lands to perennial plantings (Siddique et al. 2023). There are fewer larger-scale reviews of N₂O emission changes following perennial conversion; however, one global analysis estimated a reduction of 70% over cropland rates (He et al. 2024). Within the U.S., the COMET-Planner dataset (Swan et al. 2024) of modeled estimates approximates reductions of 60-80% at the national scale. Reductions in N₂O largely result from ceasing nitrogen fertilizer applications after removing lands from cropland production.

The broadscale estimates discussed above are likely more representative of upland plantings, which may be more analogous to Conservation Cover (327), Wildlife Habitat (420), Field Borders (386), and Herbaceous Wind Barriers (603), depending on the landscape position of these plantings. Perennial plantings downslope from croplands which are primarily intended to manage water erosion include Contour Buffer Strips (332), Vegetative Barriers (601), Grassed Waterways (412), and Riparian Herbaceous Cover (390). These downslope plantings may have different emission dynamics due to higher water and nutrient inputs.

Figure 2. Examples of upland perennial plantings.

It is difficult to compare studies across regions of the U.S. due to different soil depths measured and ages of perennial systems; however, for upland plantings, rates of soil carbon accrual seem to be higher in moist climates of the Midwest, compared to drier climates of the Great Plains. When comparing the COMET-Planner modeling results across regions of the U.S., rates in Land Resource Regions (LRR) of the western U.S. generally range from 0 – 0.2 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while LRRs in the eastern U.S. generally ranged from 0.2 - 0.4 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Swan et al. 2024). Some studies also observed distinct differences between soil textures, where finer textured soils accrued significantly more carbon than coarse textured soils (Gebhart et al. 1994, Idowu and Kircher 2016). In observations of Conservation Reserve Program lands across NE, KS, and TX, Gebhart et al. (1994) found a 4x higher rate of soil carbon accrual in loam soils compared to sandy soils.

Studies with downslope plantings were much more limited; however, data from the U.S. and Canada suggest higher rates of carbon accrual than upland plantings. A long-term study in southern Ontario (Canada) found that riparian buffer strips accumulated 3.62 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ more soil carbon than adjacent croplands (Ofusu et al. 2022). A long-term study in Missouri observed rates of 0.44 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in grass buffer strips and 0.87 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in grassed waterways (Righi et al. 2024; see Case Study). In Iowa, prairie vegetation strips incorporated into a corn-soybean cropland field at upslope, sideslope

and footslope positions accumulated significantly more surface (0-15 cm) soil carbon in sideslope and footslope positions than cropland (Perez-Sudrez et al. 2014). The prairie vegetation strips at the footslope experienced a 37% increase in soil carbon since implementation, while the footslope of a corn-soybean watershed without prairie vegetation strips lost carbon during the same time frame. Dynamics for N₂O emissions may be different in downslope plantings than upslope plantings due to nitrogen depositions from upslope cropped fields and more frequent inundation from runoff – conditions more conducive to denitrification, and greater N₂O emissions. However, studies in Indiana and Iowa of riparian buffers found that the cropped fields emitted significantly more N₂O than buffers, demonstrating that downslope plantings likely lead to N₂O reduction benefits, as well as soil carbon benefits (Fischer et al. 2014, Davis et al. 2019).

Figure 3. Perennial plantings intended to manage water erosion, or which are downslope from croplands.

If the goal of the perennial planting is to restore native soil and ecosystem function, research indicates that relatively large carbon gains accumulate in the first 1-2 decades, but that it may take over 70 years in the Southern Great Plains (Li et al. 2017) to reach levels of similar to native ecosystem soil carbon stocks, or as long as 300-400 years in tall grass prairies (Matamala et al. 2008, Rosenzweig et al. 2016). The Illinois prairie restoration study (Matamala et al. 2008) found that aboveground biomass carbon stocks reached native prairie levels after 13 years, with 50% recovery in as little as 3-5 years. Root biomass stocks lagged significantly from native prairies even after 25 years under restoration. Across all these studies, microbial biomass carbon increased with restoration age, likely reflecting increased above- and belowground carbon inputs, with the highest levels in the native soils and lowest in cultivated croplands (Li et al. 2017, Matamala et al. 2008, Rosenzweig et al. 2016). Comparisons of restoration chronosequences to native ecosystems emphasize the role of time in building biomass and soil carbon stocks, even if ecosystem restoration is not a goal for utilizing perennial plantings in agricultural landscapes.

Management Effects

SPECIES SELECTION

Most conservation practice standards evaluated in this technical guidance recommend planting locally native species, and perennial species over annual ones. The studies evaluated for this technical guidance generally also implemented native perennial species in plantings. A key question is if species diversity, specifically plantings with predominantly grasses versus grasses and forbs, affect soil carbon accrual. A large-scale meta-analysis found a positive correlation between increasing plant species diversity and soil carbon, which was more pronounced in warm climates and more arid climates (Spohn et al. 2023). The driver of the increase in soil carbon in this meta-analysis was not higher biomass production in the diverse sites but rather appears to be due to the quality of the plant organic matter inputs to the soil, as C:N ratios were higher in diverse sites.

A study in Minnesota focused on perennial bioenergy plantings did find that both above- and below-ground productivity were higher in high diversity plantings (legumes, non-legume forbs, some shrubby/woody species, and C4 and C3 grasses (plant types that are distinguished based on their use of different photosynthetic pathways)) compared to monoculture plantings, leading to higher soil carbon accrual in diverse plots (Tilman et al. 2006). This study also found that high diversity plots increased soil nitrogen by almost 25% while monoculture plots remained unchanged, likely due to the presence of legumes in high diversity plots. A long-term (33 years) prairie restoration study in southern Illinois evaluated prairies containing C4 grasses, forbs and a legume species (Ampleman et al. 2014). Forb and mixed forb/grass restorations had significantly higher rates of soil carbon sequestration compared to C4 grass-dominated restorations. Within this study, prairies were burned annually, likely leading to greater C4 domination over time and indicating management that encourages the presence of forbs may be favorable. To the extent that perennial planting Conservation Practice Standards prescribe diverse species mixes, or the inclusion of flowering forbs for pollinators or to address other resource concerns, the research supports diverse mixes, and especially mixed grass/forb systems, for building soil carbon. The inclusion of legumes may enhance productivity of the plantings by supplying nitrogen in systems that may otherwise be nitrogen-limited.

VEGETATION MANAGEMENT

When mowing or grazing are permitted or recommended in Conservation Practice Standards, there are ways to use these practices to minimize negative effects on soil carbon. A recent meta-analysis evaluated effects of management such as grazing, mowing, and burning on soil carbon stocks, including duration and frequency of events (Murindangabo et al. 2025). Long-term continuous grazing, especially with higher stocking rates, was likely to reduce carbon stocks. Short-term or improved grazing management techniques, may reduce or neutralize those losses (Conant et al. 2017). Long-term and frequent mowing similarly reduced soil carbon stocks (Murindangabo et al. 2025). This effect may be reduced by limiting frequency of mowing events and retaining cuttings to maintain organic matter in the system.

If nitrogen fertilizer is applied during the establishment period, it may increase plant production and therefore more rapidly increase soil carbon during that phase; however, mineral nitrogen fertilization will produce more substantial N₂O emissions than establishment without nitrogen fertilizer.

Case Study: Grass Buffer Strips and Grassed Waterways in a Missouri Watershed

The efficacy of grass buffer strips (Contour Buffer Strips 332) and grassed waterways (412) to manage water erosion and store soil carbon have been demonstrated in a long-term watershed study in northeastern Missouri (Figure 4). The watersheds are characterized by silt loam soils and an average precipitation of approximately 37 inches/year. The watersheds have been under no-till corn-soybean production since 1990. Buffers and grassed waterways were established in 1997.

Figure 4. The location and configuration of the Missouri Watershed study. Image from Salceda et al. (2022).

Grass buffer strip characteristics

- 3 - 4.5 m wide and spaced 36.5 m apart

- Planted to a grass-legume mix (redtop [*Agrostis gigantea* Roth], brome grass [*Bromus inermis* Leyss.], and birdsfoot trefoil [*Lotus corniculatus* L.]
- Total area: 1.3 acres

Grassed waterway characteristics

- Planted to Kentucky tall fescue grass [*Festuca arudinacea* var. genuine Schreb.]
- Total area: 1.28 acres

Soil samples were collected from the corn-soybean crop field and grass buffer strips across slope positions (upper, middle, and lower). The grassed waterway was only on the lower slope position. After 26 years, soil carbon measurements to 50 cm showed that grass buffer strips and grassed waterways built 13% and 25% more carbon than no-till corn-soybean, respectively (Figure 5) (Righi et al. 2024).

Figure 4. Soil carbon stocks to 50 cm depth after 26 years in corn-soybean, grass buffer strips, and grassed waterways.

In addition to the clear soil carbon benefits, grass buffer strips reduced sediment, nitrogen, and phosphorus losses by 28%, 13%, and 22% respectively (Udawatta et al. 2011).

Case Study: Prairie Restoration in Illinois

Grassland restorations intended to reestablish native plant communities may be analogous to Conservation Cover (327) or Wildlife Habitat (420), when those practice standards focus on native plant establishment. The Fermilab National Environmental Research Park (U.S. Dept. of Energy), near Batavia, IL, started restoring corn-soybean croplands on its grounds to tallgrass prairie in 1975. Restorations proceeded parcel by parcel over 22 years to create a long-term chronosequence to evaluate plant community and soil health recovery over time. Nearby tallgrass prairie remnants, that were presumed to not have been cultivated, provided a native reference, while corn-soybean fields provided a cultivated soil comparison. The soils at this site are mostly silt loam or silty clay loam. At the time of publication of this study (Matamala et al., 2008), restored prairies ranged from 3-25 years old.

Figure 5. Restored tallgrass prairie at the Fermilab, Batavia, IL (photo source: <https://ecology.fnal.gov/tallgrass-prairie/>).

After 25 years of successive restorations, researchers found:

- Aboveground biomass reached 50% of native remnant levels within 3-5 years and matched native levels by 13 years
- Age was a significant factor for root biomass and increased with restoration age
- Microbial biomass was lowest in the cultivated fields and highest in the remnant prairies, and increased with age in the restored prairies
- Restored prairies accrued soil carbon at a rate of $0.43 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$
- A recent study from the same site found that soil structure, specifically bulk density and soil aggregation, resembled native prairie remnants within 35 years (Scott et al. 2017)

CONCLUSION

- Conversion of cropland to perennial plantings generally increases SOC and estimates are relatively well constrained between $0.33 - 1.01 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ ($0.15 - 0.45 \text{ t C ac}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (Crews and Rumsey 2017). Nitrous oxide emissions reductions were predicted at 60-80% below cropland emission rates (He et al. 2024, Swan et al. 2024), improving the net greenhouse gas benefits of perennial plantings.
- In the assessment of regional studies, soil texture contributed greatly to the variability in SOC accrual across sites with contrasting textures. Large-scale modeling for COMET-Planner indicated higher rates of carbon accrual in more mesic climates of the eastern U.S., relative to drier climates of the western U.S. (Swan et al. 2024).

- Comparing perennial planting types (upslope vs. downslope) is difficult due to limited observations in downslope plantings, such as grass buffers or grass waterways, however the downslope plantings appear to accrue SOC at higher rates.
- If the goal of the perennial planting is to restore native soil and ecosystem function, research indicates that relatively large carbon gains accumulate in the first 1-2 decades after perennial conversion, but that it may take several decades to a few hundred years to recover native SOC stocks.
- Management of perennial plantings may affect SOC accrual rates. To the extent that perennial planting Conservation Practice Standards prescribe diverse species mixes, or the inclusion of flowering forbs for pollinators or to address other resource concerns, the research supports diverse mixes, and especially mixed grass/forb systems, for building soil carbon. Long-term and frequent haying, mowing, or grazing may undermine the building of SOC stocks in perennial plantings, so should be limited in frequency and duration.

METHODS

The literature review focused primarily on meta-analyses or ‘reviews of reviews’ to the extent they were available but also included regional and site-level experiments when meta-analyses were not available. Searches were conducted on Web of Science, Google Scholar, Google searches, and references cited in relevant studies. Search terms for response variables included soil organic carbon, soil carbon, SOC, nitrous oxide, and N₂O. Terms for perennial plantings included perennial, perennial planting(s), Conservation Reserve Program, CRP, buffer strip(s), contour buffer strip(s), vegetative barriers, wildlife habitat, riparian buffer(s), grassed waterways, land use change, grass buffers, prairie vegetation strips. Preference was given to meta-analyses or reviews in the U.S. or North America, though global analyses were also included when U.S-specific ones were not available. Further, more recent meta-analyses/reviews were favored over older ones, as the recent ones generally included the same studies as older reviews, plus newer studies. Key data from meta-analyses and other studies were recorded in a spreadsheet for assessment of prediction SOC or N₂O emission changes.

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